

(Grant Agreement 101093921)

Climate change: challenges and solutions

Set of one-pagers

WP5– Capacity building for stakeholder engagement

HORIZON-MISS-2021-CLIMA-02-05 - Local engagement of citizens in the co-creation of societal transformational change for climate resilience

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Climate change: challenges and solutions

Premise: Under the capacity building activities, Adaptation AGORA has been developing different materials. They range from multimedia materials, like videos, recordings of webinars/conferences, to sets of slides, as well as content for the development of the two Academies. Adaptation AGORA is not responsible for the use of the materials (CC BY)

1. Link to the material: See annexes

2. Potential key entries to search material

Category: Ppt

Target: Students and the general public

3. Brief Introduction/Summary

Estimated time: 50 min

Objective: Explain to the general public, who is interested, the scientific basis of climate change

Type of resource: ppt.

Language: English

4. Key Challenges/ issues addressed

The presentation addresses climate change-related topics, including the anthropogenic nature of climate change, solutions such as adaptation and mitigation measures, various scenarios, etc.

5. What the Resource Offers

A clear and practical summary of the more complex scientific aspects of climate change, made accessible to the general public.

Kliimamuutus: väljakutsed ja lahendused

Adaptation AGORA on võimekuse suurendamise eesmärgil välja töötanud erinevaid materjale, nt nagu multimeediasisu (videod, veebiseminaride/konverentside salvestused), slaidikomplektide, samuti kahe akadeemia arendamiseks mõeldud sisu. Adaptation Agora ei vastuta materjalide kasutamise eest (CC BY).

1. Link materjalile

Vt lisad

2. Võimalikud märksõnad materjali otsimiseks

Kategooria: Ppt

Sihtrühm: Õpilased ja laiem üldsus

3. Lühike sissejuhatus/kokkuvõte

Hinnanguline kestus: 50min

Eesmärk: Selgitada huvitatud üldsusele kliimamuutuste teaduslikku alust.

Ressursi tüüp: ppt

Keel: Inglise

4. Peamised väljakutsed/ lahendatavad probleemid

Ettekandes käsitletakse kliimamuutusega seotud teemasid, sealhulgas kliimamuutuse antropogeenset olemust, lahendusi, nagu kohanemis- ja leevendusmeetmed, erinevaid stsenaariume jne.

5. Mida ressurs pakub?

Kliimamuutuste keerulisemate teaduslike aspektide selge ja praktiline kokkuvõte, mis on kättesaadav laiemale üldsusele.

Changement climatique : défis et solutions

Dans le cadre des activités de renforcement des capacités, Adaptation AGORA a développé différents supports. Ceux-ci incluent des contenus multimédias, tels que des vidéos, enregistrements de webinaires/conférences, des ensembles de diapositives, ainsi que des contenus pour le développement de deux Académies. L'utilisation de ces contenus, mis à disposition sous licence Creative Commons (CC BY), relève de la responsabilité des utilisateurs et non du projet Adaptation Agora.

1. Lien vers le contenu: Voir annexes

2. Entrées clés potentielles pour rechercher du matériel :

Catégorie et cible : Catégorie : Ppt Cible : Étudiants et grand public

3. Brève introduction/résumé:

Temps estimé : 50 min

Objectif : Expliquer au grand public intéressé les fondements scientifiques du changement climatique.

Type de ressource: ppt

Langue: Anglais

4. Principaux défis/problèmes abordés:

La présentation aborde des thèmes liés au changement climatique, notamment la nature anthropique du changement climatique, les solutions telles que les mesures d'adaptation et d'atténuation, divers scénarios, etc.

5. Apports de la ressource:

Un résumé clair et pratique des aspects scientifiques plus complexes du changement climatique, rendu accessible au grand public.

Klimawandel: Herausforderungen und Lösungen

Im Rahmen der "Hilfe zur Selbsthilfe" - Aktivitäten hat das Projekt Adaptation AGORA verschiedene Materialien entwickelt. Diese beinhalten multimediale Inhalte wie Videos, Aufzeichnungen von Webinaren/Konferenzen, Foliensätze sowie Inhalte für die Entwicklung der beiden Online-Akademien. Adaptation AGORA ist nicht verantwortlich für die Nutzung der Ressourcen (CC BY).

1. Link zum Material: siehe Anhang

2. Potenzielle Suchbegriffe:

Kategorie: Ppt

Zielgruppe: Studierende und die allgemeine Öffentlichkeit

3. Kurze Einführung/Zusammenfassung:

Geschätzte Zeit: 50min

Ziel: Der interessierten Öffentlichkeit die wissenschaftlichen Grundlagen des Klimawandels erklären.

Materialtyp: ppt.

Sprache: Englisch

4. Zentrale Herausforderungen/Probleme, die adressiert werden:

Die Präsentation befasst sich mit Themen des Klimawandels, darunter die anthropogene Natur des Klimawandels, Lösungen wie Klimaschutz- und Anpassungsmaßnahmen, verschiedene Szenarien usw.

5. Was das Material bietet:

Eine klare und praktische Zusammenfassung der komplexeren wissenschaftlichen Aspekte des Klimawandels, die der breiten Öffentlichkeit zugänglich gemacht werden.

Κλιματική αλλαγή: προκλήσεις και λύσεις

Σημείωση: Στο πλαίσιο των δραστηριοτήτων ανάπτυξης ικανοτήτων, το πρόγραμμα Adaptation AGORA έχει δημιουργήσει επιμορφωτικό και εκπαιδευτικό υλικό. Αυτό περιλαμβάνει πολυμεσικό υλικό, όπως βίντεο, μαγνητοσκοπημένα διαδικτυακά σεμινάρια/συνεδρία, παρουσιάσεις, καθώς και το περιεχόμενο που χρησιμοποιήθηκε για την ανάπτυξη των δύο διαδικτυακών Ακαδημιών. Το Adaptation Agora δεν φέρει ευθύνη για τη χρήση των υλικών (CC BY).

1. Σύνδεσμος προς το υλικό: βλέπε παραρτήματα

2. Πιθανοί βασικοί όροι αναζήτησης του υλικού:

Κατηγορία: Ppt

Ομάδες-στόχοι: Φοιτητές και ευρύ κοινό

3. Σύντομη εισαγωγή/περίληψη:

Εκτιμώμενος χρόνος: 50 λεπτά

Σκοπός: Επεξήγηση της επιστημονικής βάσης της κλιματικής αλλαγής στο ευρύ κοινό

Τύπος υλικού: ppt

Γλώσσα: Αγγλικά

4. Βασικές προκλήσεις/ζητήματα που αντιμετωπίζονται:

Η παρουσίαση εξετάζει θέματα που σχετίζονται με την κλιματική αλλαγή, όπως η ανθρωπογενής φύση της κλιματικής αλλαγής, λύσεις όπως μέτρα προσαρμογής και μετριασμού, διάφορα σενάρια κ.λπ.

5. Τι προσφέρει το υλικό:

Μια σαφής και πρακτική σύνοψη των πιο σύνθετων επιστημονικών πτυχών της κλιματικής αλλαγής, διατυπωμένη με τρόπο προσιτό στο ευρύ κοινό.

Cambiamento Climatico: sfide e soluzioni

Nell'ambito delle attività di capacity building, Adaptation AGORA ha sviluppato diversi materiali che spaziano da contenuti multimediali, come video e registrazioni di webinar/conferenze, presentazioni in power point, nonché contenuti per lo sviluppo delle due Accademie.

Adaptation Agora non è responsabile dell'utilizzo dei materiali (CC BY)

1. Link Alla risorsa: vedi allegati

2. Parole chiave per cercare la risorsa

Categoria: presentazione power point

Destinatari: pubblico generale, studenti

3. Sintesi

Tempo stimato per la consultazione della risorsa: 50min

Obiettivo: Spiegare al pubblico generale e a chi è interessato quali sono le basi scientifiche del cambiamento climatico

Tipo di risorsa: presentazione power point

Lingua: Inglese

4. Principali sfide/problematiche affrontate

La presentazione affronta temi legati al cambiamento climatico, inclusa la natura antropica del fenomeno, le soluzioni come le misure di adattamento e mitigazione, i vari scenari, ecc.

5. Cosa offre la risorsa

Un riassunto chiaro e pratico degli aspetti scientifici più complessi del cambiamento climatico, reso accessibile al grande pubblico.

Cambio climático: retos y soluciones

En el marco de las actividades de desarrollo de capacidades, Adaptation AGORA ha elaborado diversos materiales. Estos abarcan desde materiales multimedia, como vídeos y grabaciones de seminarios web y conferencias, hasta conjuntos de diapositivas, así como contenidos para el desarrollo de las dos academias. Adaptation Agora no se hace responsable del uso de los materiales (CC BY).

1. Enlace al material: Ver anexos

2. Posibles entradas clave para buscar el material.

Categoría: Presentación

Target: Estudiantes y público general

3. Breve introducción/resumen

Tiempo estimado: 50min

Objetivo: Explicar al público en general interesado las bases científicas del cambio climático

Tipo de recurso: ppt

Idioma: Inglés

4. Retos clave/temas abordados

La presentación aborda temas relacionados con el cambio climático, como la naturaleza antropogénica del cambio climático, soluciones como las medidas de adaptación y mitigación, y cuáles son los escenarios, etc.

5. Qué ofrece el recurso

Un resumen claro y práctico de los aspectos científicos más complejos del cambio climático, accesible al público en general.

Klimatförändringar: utmaningar och lösningar

Adaptation AGORA har tagit fram olika material för kapacitetsutveckling. Dessa inkluderar allt från multimedieinnehåll, såsom videor och inspelningar av webbseminarier och konferenser, till bildsamlingar och material för utvecklingen av de två akademierna. Adaptation AGORA ansvarar inte för hur materialen används (CC BY).

1. Länk till materialet: Se bilagor

2. Potentiella sökord

Kategori: Ppt

Målgrupp: Studenter och allmänheten

3. Kort introduktion/sammanfattning

Beräknad tid: 50min

Syfte: Att förklara den vetenskapliga grunden för klimatförändringarna för den allmänhet som är intresserad.

Typ av resurs: Powerpoint-presentation

Språk: Engelska

4. Centrala utmaningar/problem som behandlas

Presentationens innehåll omfattar klimatförändringsrelaterade frågor, inklusive dess antropogena orsaker, lösningar i form av klimatanpassning och utsläppsminskningar, olika scenarier och mer därtill.

5. Vad resursen erbjuder

En tydlig och praktisk sammanfattning av de mer komplexa vetenskapliga aspekterna av klimatförändringarna. Ökad tillgänglighet för allmänheten.

Annex: Resource

Funded by the European Union

Climate, climate variability and climate change

CLIMATE VARIABILITY means the variability of a specific climatic quantity (for example the temperature of the earth's surface) around its average value (observed over a long period). These variations are linked to year-to-year variations (interannual and seasonal) and to ten-year oscillations, which overlap with the average value of the quantity.

CLIMATE CHANGE: statistically significant changes in the average state of the climate or in its variability, persisting for an extended period. Even with reference to climate change, the concept of fluctuation of climatic quantities must be associated, but these quantities oscillate around a new average value which, together with all those calculated over a long period of time, define a **climate trend**.

The IPCC graph (2001) illustrates how a shift and/or flattening of a temperature probability distribution has notable consequences on the probability of occurrence of extreme events

The anthropogenic nature of climate change

Certainty about the human cause of CC

1990 «emissions from human activities are substantially increasing the concentration of greenhouse gases in the atmosphere» (1st IPCC Report)
1995 «These trends [increasing concentrations of greenhouse gases in the atmosphere] can be largely attributed to human activities» (2nd IPCC Report)
2001 «in light of the new evidence and taking into account the remaining uncertainties; it is possible to state that the warming observed in the last 50 years is due to the increase in the concentration of greenhouse gases» (3rd IPCC Report)
2007 «Most of the observed increase in global average temperatures since the mid-20th century is most likely due to the observed increase in concentrations of anthropogenic greenhouse gases» (4th IPCC Report)
2013 «Human influence on the climate system is clear and recent anthropogenic greenhouse gas emissions are the highest in history with widespread impacts on human and natural systems» (5th IPCC Report)
2021 «The observed increases in greenhouse gas (GHG) concentrations since around 1750 are unambiguously caused by human activities. Since 2011, concentrations in the atmosphere have continued to increase, reaching annual averages of 410 ppm for carbon dioxide (CO₂), 1,866 ppb for methane (CH₄), and 332 ppb for nitrous oxide (N₂O) in 2019 (6th IPCC Report).

The relevance of observations in the study of climate change

Studying the Earth's climate in detail has been possible due to the great increase in new observation systems, particularly those based on satellite measurements, which have increased the number of observations of the Earth's climate system by an order of magnitude.

The Iride project, the result of collaboration between the Italian government and the European Space Agency, uses resources from the PNRR and aims to provide satellite services to support various public entities, such as Civil Protection, in the management of emergencies such as hydrogeological disruptions, fires, protection of coasts, monitoring of critical infrastructures, air quality and meteorological conditions.

What the observations tell us

- Atmosphere and ocean have warmed; The extent and volume of the ice have reduced;
- Sea levels have risen;
- The increase in CO₂ has caused the pH of the ocean to decrease (ocean acidification);
- Snow cover in the Northern Hemisphere has decreased;
- Intensification of the water cycle with more intense rainfall and floods, while in other regions extreme droughts.

Many of these changes have not been reflected in the past two millennia...

How the future will look like

Starting from the following facts:

The characteristics of the climate on both a global and local scale are therefore influenced by the concentration of climate-altering gases in the atmosphere. These concentrations also depend on anthropogenic emissions as well as on natural factors themselves variable in time and space, the variation of the former depends on us... on how much we emit in terms of climate-altering gases. These concentrations appear to tend to increase further in the coming years.

This acknowledged, in order to understand how the climate evolves, we need:

- To know the dynamics that govern climate processes
- To know how these concentrations will change

Climate models are developed just for this purpose.

Global climate change scenarios - temperature

IPCC, 2021: Summary for Policymakers, In: Climate Change 2021: The Physical Science Basis. Contribution of Working Group I to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change. Cambridge University Press.

Temperature variation due to global warming

Global climate change scenarios - precipitation

IPCC, 2021: Summary for Policymakers, In: Climate Change 2021: The Physical Science Basis. Contribution of Working Group I to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change. Cambridge University Press.

A global problem with local characteristics

Precipitation variation due to global warming

Climate change scenarios for Italy (maps and results from PNACC)

Scenarios defined as part of the IPCC Fifth Assessment Report

RCP2.6 ("Aggressive mitigation", with emissions halved by 2050).

RCP4.5 ("strong stabilization", with significant reductions in emissions).

RCP8.5 ("No mitigation")

Max precipitation in one day

- General increase in heat waves.
- Significant increase in fire danger particularly in the Apennines and Alps.
- Increase in the number of drought episodes, particularly in southern Italy (including the islands).
- For the most extreme storm surges, an increase is expected, especially in the upper Adriatic, Ligurian Sea and upper Tyrrhenian Sea.
- General increase in the intensity and frequency of extreme precipitation events.
- Decrease in overall annual precipitation (up to 20% in 2050).

From climate change to climate risks

The IPCC identifies four key risk categories for Europe. The level of each risk increases as the level of global warming increases.

Risks of heat waves on populations and ecosystems

Number of deaths and people at risk of heat stress doubled or tripled for a temperature rise of 3.5 degrees compared to 1.5. Reduction of habitats suitable for current terrestrial and marine ecosystems and irreversible change in their composition. Adaptation measures must be anticipated in southern Europe, where the risk is greater than in northern areas.

Risks produced by greater frequency and intensity of floods

Due to changes in precipitations and rising sea levels, risks to people and infrastructure from coastal, river and pluvial flooding will increase in many regions of Europe.

Risks for agricultural production

Due to a combination of heat and drought, substantial losses in agricultural production are expected in the 21st century for most areas of Europe, which will not be offset by the gains expected for Northern Europe.

Risks of scarcity of water resources

In southern Europe the risk is already high for a level of global warming of 1.5 degrees and becomes very high in the case of a rise of 3 degrees. In these regions, the demand for water resources already exceeds availability. In the case of a temperature rise of 3 degrees, the risk of water scarcity becomes high even in central-Western Europe.

P. Lionello <https://ipccitalia.cmcc.it/il-rapporto-ippc-spiegato-dagli-esperti-italiani-con-i-contenuti-principali-su-europa-mediterraneo-e-italia/>

The impact of the increase in heat waves on the population of cities

Average annual deaths in summer attributable to heat waves for the period 2021-2050 according to the RCP4.5 scenario

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³ C.I.R.A. - Centro Italiano Ricerche Atmosferiche

Economic impacts in Italy

The higher the temperature, the higher the costs

The economic impacts of climate change in Italy appear to still be manageable although they present non-negligible costs, around 0.5 of the national GDP, only for temperature increases of less than 2 degrees compared to the pre-industrial period. For higher temperature increases, costs increase rapidly and exponentially. For example, in the high emissions climate scenario, which predicts an average temperature increase of 4 degrees compared to the pre-industrial period at the end of the last century, the losses in GDP per capita would be higher than 2.5% in 2050 and between 7-8 % at the end of the century.

The most affected sectors

All sectors of the Italian economy are negatively impacted by climate change, however the greatest losses occur in the country's networks and infrastructure, as a consequence of the intensification of hydrogeological instability phenomena, in agriculture and in the tourism sector in the segments both summer and winter.

Inequalities

Climate change increases economic inequality between regions. Negative economic impacts tend to be higher in relatively poorer areas. For example, in an RCP8.5 scenario, equality indicators worsen by 16% in 2050 and 61% in 2080.

DOI: 10.25424/cmcc/analisi_del_rischio

The solutions

Mitigation

Scenarios defined as part of the IPCC Fifth Assessment Report

- ❖ RCP2.6 ("Aggressive mitigation")
- ❖ RCP4.5 ("Strong stabilization")
- ❖ RCP8.5 ("No mitigation")

Temporal trend, up to 2100, of the annual average of the average daily temperature at national level, considering an ensemble of EURO-CORDEX models

